

FUNDAMENTAL THEORETICAL CONCEPTS OF LINGUODIDACTICS AND THEIR PEDAGOGICAL SIGNIFICANCE

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Abstract: This article examines the concept of digital education, its role in the modern learning environment, and the integration of digital technologies into foreign language teaching. It provides an overview of the historical development of digital education, tracing its evolution from early computer-assisted instruction to contemporary educational systems powered by artificial intelligence. The paper analyzes the pedagogical, technological, and socio-cultural factors that have influenced the formation of digital education.

Keywords: Digital education, foreign language teaching, educational technology, digital tools, ICT in education, artificial intelligence in education, personalized learning, digital pedagogy, online learning, blended learning, digital transformation.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается концепция цифрового образования, подчеркивается его значимость в современном образовательном пространстве и анализируется интеграция цифровых технологий в преподавание иностранных языков. Представлен обзор исторического развития цифрового образования — от первых моделей компьютерного обучения до современных образовательных систем на основе искусственного интеллекта. В статье проводится критический анализ педагогических, технологических и социокультурных факторов, повлиявших на становление и развитие цифрового образования.

Ключевые слова: Цифровое образование, преподавание иностранных языков, образовательные технологии, цифровые инструменты, ИКТ в образовании, искусственный интеллект в обучении, персонализированное обучение, цифровая педагогика, онлайн-обучение, смешанное обучение, цифровая трансформация.

In recent years, the term linguodidactics has been increasingly employed in modern linguistics. The field of linguodidactics emerged at the intersection of linguistics and didactics, focusing on the scientific study of language learning and teaching processes. Linguodidactics (from Latin *lingua* – “language” and Greek *didaktikos* – “instructive”) refers to the general theory of language learning. The term was introduced into academic discourse by Academician N. M. Shansky with the aim of addressing issues related to the description of language within the educational process.

As a scientific discipline, linguodidactics emerged in the second half of the 20th century—more precisely, in 1969—when Academician N. M. Shansky introduced it in the context of academic descriptions of language-related problems. Initially, it was mainly applied within the framework of teaching Russian as a foreign language. According to Shansky, linguodidactics encompasses

the distinctive features, content, and structure of language learning, as well as other issues falling within the scientific research domains of pedagogy and linguistics.

In A.N. Shukin's *Lingvodidactic Encyclopedic Dictionary*, the difference between lingvodidactics and language teaching methodology is explained as follows: Lingvodidactics is the theory of language teaching that develops the foundations of language instruction, whereas methodology refers to the process of language learning. Today, lingvodidactics, like language teaching methodology, studies foreign language as an academic subject, interpreting language both as a goal and as a means of education. It develops at the intersection of pedagogy, didactics, linguistics, and psychology. Lingvodidactics studies not only issues related to language teaching but also the human use of language and pays attention to the practical aspects of language teaching, i.e., the process itself. The development of lingvodidactics as a science is based on synthesizing the analytical and empirical components of methodological knowledge in foreign language teaching, its object, subject, and research tasks. This science incorporates many fields of knowledge and studies the interrelations between language, consciousness, culture, and society, the processes of foreign language teaching, language acquisition as part of education, and language use as a communication tool.

According to the concept developed by V. Reinecke, there are three independent but interrelated scientific fields that form the theory of foreign language teaching: 1) theory of language teaching or lingvodidactics; 2) didactics of foreign language; and 3) specific language teaching or special methodology.¹

When describing the scope of lingvodidactic research, reference is made to the concept of "professional language user" or "linguistic personality" to characterize research directions. This involves outlining the distinctive and innovative features of the modern sociocultural model of language education, its key components, including the significance, goals, content, and methods of such education, as well as emphasizing students' communicative activity, their involvement in social relations, and educational outcomes.

Undoubtedly, the development of lingvodidactics or foreign language teaching theory determines the quality of foreign language learning. Currently, the science of lingvodidactics is expanding the scope of research in the field of foreign language teaching, opening new scientific directions and approaches, particularly through integrating language with professional fields in the education system.

Lingvodidactic description includes studying similarities and differences between languages, analyzing the content and structure of the target language, and addressing other issues arising at the intersection of linguistics and pedagogy. However, specialists do not have a unanimous opinion on the content and necessity of this term. Some scholars accept lingvodidactics as a

¹ [Reinecke, W. (1983). *Zur Theorie des Fremdspracherwerbs – ein methodologischer Ansatz* / W. Reinecke; trans. from German. Moscow: Academy, pp. 257–263.]

term covering the theoretical and practical problems of language teaching, essentially used instead of the term methodology.²

The main goal of lingvodidactics is to produce and systematize reliable knowledge in foreign language teaching. Its main problems can be divided into two groups.

The first group relates to the composition and history of scientific methodological knowledge, its principles, forms, and methods, while the second group provides the possibility of applying this knowledge in the educational process. Thus, at every stage of lingvodidactics development, the acquired scientific-methodological knowledge is both the object and the product of the learning process.

The second group, in turn, is interpreted as a specific scientific activity aimed at producing, generalizing, and systematizing scientific knowledge within the scope of lingvodidactics, including its integration into certain concepts, approaches, models, techniques, and the educational process.

Therefore, this suggests that lingvodidactics is the product of scientific and methodological research as a theory of foreign language teaching, and its main research object is the set of scientific concepts about learning and teaching foreign languages. Studying these issues in detail through an integrated curriculum, as well as investigating the evolutionary and innovative development of the discipline and the related cognitive processes, is one of the important topics on today's agenda.

In recent years, lingvodidactics has incorporated digital technologies, such as language learning applications, virtual classrooms, and artificial intelligence. This approach not only increases learning efficiency but also provides personalized education for students.

The lingvodidactic principles of digital tools are applied in language teaching through digital applications as follows:

- **Enhancing motivation:** Students become engaged in the learning process through interactive games and tasks.
- **Individualization:** Each student can choose activities that correspond to their abilities and knowledge level. For example, applications like Duolingo offer students tasks tailored to their proficiency level.

The lingvodidactic basis of foreign language teaching enables the formation and development of the learner's competencies. The concepts of competence and competency, as pedagogical notions, have their own essence, structure, and classification. N.B. Elukhina, in her research, analyzed discourse competence and its significance in professional communication; O.B. Kudryashova conducted studies on the components of communicative competence in teaching written speech; N.I. Arshinova examined the formation of linguistic competence in learning

² Shansky N.M. (1985). Russian Linguistics and Lingvodidactics: collection of articles. Moscow: Russian Language, p. 228; Shukin A.N. (2007). Lingvodidactic Encyclopedic Dictionary: more than 2000 entries.

English as a second specialty using ICT tools; I.B. Burtovaya studied communicative competence and the social-psychological factors in its development; J. Jalolov analyzed the formation of professional competence for future specialists, while P.N. Pijova carried out research on the psychological competence of leaders. Didactics, in a broad sense, considers all aspects of teaching and learning as a whole. Below, following the opinion of I. Vorozhtsova, we briefly outline the main theoretical concepts of lingvodidactics and their explanations.

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